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Entrepreneurship Education & Training Landscape in Secondary Schools of Rwanda and Kenya

Policy and Practice Pathways
for Impact

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Executive summary

This report was commissioned by the Allan & Gill Gray Philanthropies East Africa (AGGPEA) in order to provide a consolidated analysis of the entrepreneurship education (EE) and training landscape in secondary schools across Rwanda and Kenya. It draws on three complementary research components—a Bibliometric Analysis, a Systematic Literature Review (SLR), and a Global Online Scan of EE best practices and organizational typologies—to offer a multi-dimensional understanding of how EE is evolving within these two East African countries. The study addressed six interlinked objectives (see Section One): including mapping the EE landscape, understanding key ecosystem actors, identifying gaps and policy levers, and extracting globally informed pathways for effective implementation.

The **Bibliometric Analysis** is based on Scopus and Web of Science data. 10 peer reviewed papers were used to assess the landscape of EE in secondary schools in Rwanda and Kenya. These were complemented by 552 peer-reviewed papers used to assess the EE landscape worldwide while 201 were used for the EE landscape for Africa. The results from the analysis conducted revealed a modest but growing body of EE research. However, African-led scholarship remains limited, with much of the work driven by international collaborations. The analysis highlighted critical gaps in policy-oriented studies, localized pedagogical insights, and representation of secondary school-level interventions.

The **Systematic Literature Review**, covering 23 peer-reviewed studies published between 2015 and 2025 to examine the landscape of EE in secondary schools in Kenya and Rwanda. Guided by four of the six overall research project objectives, the SLR mapped program types, assessed actors and delivery mechanisms, and identified challenges such as inadequate teacher training, fragmented stakeholder coordination, limited infrastructure, and underdeveloped local models. The findings underscore the need for targeted investment, policy alignment, and institutional collaboration to position EE as a driver of youth empowerment and inclusive economic growth.

To supplement these two knowledge products, we conducted a **Global Online Scan of Best Practices**. This component identified typologies of organizations supporting EE—including NGOs, public-private partnerships, government programs, and donor-funded initiatives. We reviewed how digital technologies, including artificial intelligence, are being applied to scale EE globally. The analysis surfaced scalable, cost-effective models that offer strategic lessons for East African implementation, particularly the Kenyan and Rwandan governments and ecosystem partners.

Together, these knowledge products inform a set of forward-looking recommendations. These include strengthening institutional frameworks, investing in teacher capacity development, aligning local efforts with global benchmarks, enhancing M&E systems, and supporting African-led EE research. The report emphasizes the importance of context-driven, collaborative approaches to catalyze entrepreneurship education as a core pillar for youth development and economic resilience in Kenya and Rwanda.

Note: While this report draws on a wide range of sources and data points, in-text citations have been intentionally excluded to enhance readability. All references are listed in the final section of the report. Readers seeking deeper attribution or methodological details are encouraged to consult the full SLR and Bibliometric papers we can provide separately on request.

Report structure

This report is organized to present a multi-faceted understanding of the entrepreneurship education (EE) and training landscape in Kenya and Rwanda. It brings together findings from three interconnected components: a Bibliometric Analysis, a Systematic Literature Review (SLR), and a Global Online Scan of Actors and Best Practices. Each section contributes to addressing the research objectives.

- **Section 1 (Introduction)** provides background, rationale, scope, and alignment with national and continental goals.
- **Section 2 (Methodology)** outlines the approaches used for the three research components.
- **Section 3 (Findings)** is divided into three parts: global best practices (bibliometric trends), national EE landscapes (SLR), and mapping of actors and EE initiatives.
- **Section 4 (Discussion)** synthesizes cross-cutting themes and implications.
- **Section 5 (Recommendations)** presents targeted policy and programmatic guidance for key stakeholders.
- **Sections 6–7** include the conclusion, references, and annexes with supporting data, figures, and tools.

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Acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym	Description
ACM	Association for Computing Machinery
AGGP EA	Allan & Gill Gray Philanthropy East Africa
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ASALs	Arid and Semi-Arid Lands
CBC	Competency-Based Curriculum
CPD	Continuous Professional Development
EdTech	Education Technology
EE	Entrepreneurship Education
EMIS	Education Management Information System
ERIC	Education Resources Information Center
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
M&E	Monitoring and Evaluation
MINEDUC	Ministry of Education (Rwanda)
MoE	Ministry of Education (Kenya or general)
MTP	Medium-Term Plan
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
RCT	Randomized Controlled Trial
RePEc	Research Papers in Economics
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SLR	Systematic Literature Review
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
TTCs	Teacher Training Colleges
TVET	Technical and Vocational Education and Training
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
VOSviewer	Visualization of Similarities Viewer (a bibliometric analysis tool)
WoS	Web of Science

Section one | Introduction

Introduction

This section outlines the background, purpose, and scope of our study on Entrepreneurship Education (EE) in secondary schools in Kenya and Rwanda. It highlights the rationale for the study, its alignment with national development goals, and key continental goals by African Union. The section also outlines the scope and limitations, providing context for the study's evidence-based approach and strategic relevance.

Background and Rationale

Entrepreneurship education is increasingly recognized as a key lever for addressing youth unemployment, fostering innovation, and equipping learners with problem solving and value creation skills. In Kenya and Rwanda, EE is being mainstreamed into national education reforms, including the adoption of Competency-Based Curricula (CBC). These efforts reflect a growing recognition of the role EE can play in shaping self-reliant, future-ready youth capable of navigating dynamic economic landscapes.

Despite these advances, the implementation of EE in secondary schools remains uneven, under-researched, and poorly documented. Gaps persist in teacher capacity, pedagogical approaches, resource access, and coordination among actors. Furthermore, emerging global practices, including the use of digital and artificial intelligence (AI)-driven tools in EE, remain largely untapped in the East African context.

Purpose of the Study

This report consolidates a multi-faceted understanding of the EE and Training landscape in secondary schools across Kenya and Rwanda, while identifying strategic opportunities for intervention and scale. It brings together insights from Systematic Literature Review (SLR), Bibliometric Analysis, and Global Scan of best practices and EE organizations.

The study objectives were to:

- **Search, document, and present global best practices** in EE, focusing on countries where such practices could inform implementation in Kenya and Rwanda. This includes interventions using emerging technologies such as Artificial Intelligence.
- **Map the current EE landscape** in secondary schools in Rwanda and Kenya, identifying existing programs, challenges, and opportunities—including how EE is embedded in core and extracurricular activities.
- **Understand the EE ecosystem** by developing a typology of key providers (e.g., educational institutions, policymakers, NGOs), their technical specializations, geographic coverage, and alignment with government strategies.
- **Highlight implementation gaps**, focusing on issues like curriculum design, pedagogy, teacher training, and resource availability.
- **Identify policy interventions** that can accelerate the growth and institutionalization of EE in secondary schools.
- **Propose actionable pathways and interventions**, grounded in global standards, to guide developmental organizations and their partners in deploying effective EE initiatives in the region.

Relevance to National Goals, and African Union's Agenda 2063

This study aligns directly with the mission to support entrepreneurship and inclusive education systems that create sustainable social and economic value. It contributes actionable insights for designing scalable and impactful EE programs that can benefit national goals and regional initiatives.

At the national level, the study supports Kenya Vision 2030 and Rwanda Vision 2050, both of which prioritize youth empowerment, skills development, and innovation. The research also reinforces the implementation of Competency-Based Curricula (CBC) in both countries.

Continently, the study contributes to several aspirations and goals of African Union's Agenda 2063, including:

- Aspiration 1 (Goal 2): Well Educated Citizens and Skills revolution underpinned by Science, Technology and Innovation, by embedding entrepreneurship education in national school systems.
- Aspiration 6 (Goal 18): Engaged and empowered youth and children, by promoting learner-centered EE that enhances creativity, agency, and economic opportunity.
- Aspiration 7 (Goal 19): Africa as a major partner in global affairs, by aligning EE strategies with global innovation trends and scalable digital models.

Scope and Limitations

This study focused on secondary school-level EE programs in Kenya and Rwanda, emphasizing formal and non-formal education settings. The scope included peer-reviewed academic literature (SLR), bibliometric data from Scopus and Web of Science, and global scan of best practice platforms and organizational models.

While the methodology triangulates multiple sources to ensure robustness, several limitations exist:

- The bibliometric analysis may underrepresent locally published or grey literature not indexed in high-quality international academic databases.
- Whereas the bibliometric analysis covered an unspecified timeframe, the Systematic Literature Review focused on publications from 2015 to 2025, which may have excluded earlier yet relevant initiatives.
- The global scan did not involve in-depth country case studies or interviews, which limits contextual interpretation of some best practices. Case studies or stakeholder interviews can complement this effort but beyond the scope of this research.

Despite these limitations, the findings provide a solid foundation for designing and scaling EE programs that are both locally responsive and globally informed.

Section two | Methodology

Introduction

This study employed a mixed-methods approach to generate a comprehensive understanding of the EE and Training landscape in Kenya and Rwanda, and to identify relevant global best practices. Three interlinked components were used: a SLR, a Bibliometric Analysis, and a Global Scan of actors and EE initiatives. Each component was triangulated to address specific objectives and to complement the others to ensure analytical depth and practical relevance.

Bibliometric Analysis

This study applied bibliometric analysis to map the global and regional landscape of EE research, particularly in secondary school contexts. Bibliometric analysis allows for a structured, quantitative approach to reviewing literature, revealing patterns in authorship, collaboration, and thematic focus across countries and regions. The method complements the systematic review by offering a macro-level perspective on scholarly production and visibility, helping identify key trends and research gaps.

Approach

- **Database Selection:** Data was extracted from **Scopus** and **Web of Science** using a comprehensive set of search terms relevant to EE in secondary schools, both globally and specifically for Kenya and Rwanda.
 - **Global and African search terms included:** "entrepreneurship education in high schools", "entrepreneurship education in secondary schools", "entrepreneurship learning", "entrepreneurship training", "entrepreneurship curriculum", "student entrepreneurship", "gamified online entrepreneurship", and others.
 - **Kenya and Rwanda specific search terms included:** "entrepreneurial learning", "entrepreneurship programs", "secondary school entrepreneurs", "youth entrepreneurs", "Wavumbuzi entrepreneurship program", and similar variations.
- **Tools:** Analytical software such as **VOSviewer** and **Bibliometrix (R Studio)** were used to visualize keyword co-occurrence networks, author collaboration maps, and global/regional publication distributions.

Key Outputs

- **Publication Volume and Growth:** There is a steady growth in EE-related publications since 2010, with a noticeable increase post-2020, particularly in digital EE and gamified approaches—reflecting shifts driven by remote learning needs.
- **Geographical Distribution:** The global EE research landscape is dominated by contributions from North America, Europe, and parts of Asia. Africa represents a small proportion of the total publications, with Kenya and Rwanda collectively accounting for fewer than 20 peer-reviewed articles in this domain over the 24-year period.
- **Authorship Patterns:** A significant proportion of publications on EE in Africa are led by non-African researchers, indicating limited African-led authorship and external reliance for visibility and publication.

- **Co-Occurrence and Keyword Mapping:**
 - **Globally**, keywords such as “entrepreneurial mindset”, “experiential learning”, and “digital tools” were most prevalent.
 - In **Africa**, themes were more focused on “youth employment”, “skills development”, and “TVET”.
 - In **Kenya and Rwanda**, frequently occurring terms included “secondary school entrepreneurship,” “curriculum reform,” and “youth empowerment,” though overall frequency remained low.
- **Collaboration and Institutional Affiliation:** Most Kenya- and Rwanda-based EE research was conducted in collaboration with international institutions. Common affiliations included local public universities in partnership with donor-funded projects or academic networks.
- **Research Gaps Identified:**
 - A modest but growing body of EE scholarship in East Africa.
 - Limited implementation-focused and policy-aligned research.
 - Underrepresentation of digital innovation, informal learning models, and inclusive approaches tailored to underserved populations.

Implications

The bibliometric analysis highlights an urgent need to amplify locally led, context-relevant EE research that addresses implementation challenges in real school environments. Enhancing African research visibility, especially on policy and practice, will be critical in shaping effective EE strategies grounded in regional realities.

Systematic Literature Review (SLR)

The SLR was conducted to map the existing EE landscape in secondary schools in Kenya and Rwanda. It aimed to identify current programs, key ecosystem actors, implementation challenges, policy gaps, and strategic opportunities for strengthening EE systems in both countries.

Approach

The review followed the **PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses)** framework to ensure methodological transparency and rigor. A structured data extraction template (Table 3 in the Annexes Section) was used to code relevant study characteristics, interventions, and findings.

Key steps included:

- **Inclusion Criteria:** Peer-reviewed journal articles published between 2015 and 2025 that addressed EE in secondary school contexts within Kenya or Rwanda.
- **Database Search:** Targeted searches were conducted in major academic databases, including Scopus, Web of Science, EconPapers (RePEc), ProQuest, ERIC, and ACM Digital Library. Boolean search strings used included:
 - TITLE-ABS-KEY: (Entrepreneur* AND (Education* OR Training OR Promotion OR Learning) AND (Rwanda* OR Kenya*)) AND (“secondary school” OR “high school”)
 - Entrepreneur* AND Education* OR Training OR Learning OR Promotion AND Rwanda* OR Kenya* AND Junior OR Secondary OR High AND School
- **Screening and Selection:** After applying inclusion and exclusion criteria, 23 articles were retained for in-depth review and thematic synthesis.
- **Data Extraction:** An Excel-based data extraction template was used to organize findings by author, methodology, country, intervention type, target group, key results, identified gaps, policy relevance, technology use, and alignment with national strategies (see Table 3 in the Annexes Section).

Key Outputs

The SLR generated several important insights:

- **Geographical focus:** Most studies focused on Rwanda (61%), while Kenya accounted for around 30%, with some covering both countries or regional contexts (refer to Figure 8).
- **Methodological distribution:** Most studies (52.2%) employed qualitative methodologies, while 21.7% used Randomized Controlled Trials (RCTs) and another 21.7% applied mixed methods. Only 4.3% were policy documents, reflecting a diverse yet predominantly qualitative research landscape (Figure 7).
- **Mapping of EE Program Types:** The studies revealed a diverse range of EE interventions. Co-curricular programs were the most prominent (10 studies), followed by curriculum-based interventions (4) and teacher training initiatives (2). A few studies explored more integrated or specialized themes such as policy engagement, instructional approaches, psychological factors, and institutional ecosystem development. Some programs combined multiple dimensions—such as curriculum, co-curricular, and policy partnerships—highlighting the growing complexity and cross-cutting nature of EE implementation.
- **Target Group Focus:** The studies captured a wide array of target audiences within the EE landscape. Notably, five studies simultaneously focused on both Secondary School Students and Teachers, reflecting an integrated approach to learner and educator development. In contrast, two studies focused solely on Secondary School Students, without an explicit teacher training or educator component. Other individual studies explored specialized groups including Out-of-School Youth (12–17 years), TVET students, Curriculum Developers, Policymakers, Adolescent Girls and Club Mentors, Aspiring Digital Content Creators, and EE Program Partners. This diversity illustrates the broadening reach of EE beyond traditional learners to encompass multiple ecosystem actors.
- **Implementation Challenges:** Recurring issues included inadequate teacher training, limited pedagogical tools, and unequal access to learning resources—particularly in rural contexts.
- **Policy and Practice Gaps:** Although both countries have embedded EE within their Competency-Based Curricula (CBC), there is often a disconnect between policy intent and school-level implementation, especially where institutional capacity is weak or fragmented.
- **Use of Technology in EE:** Although digital transformation is central to modern education systems, only a few studies integrated ICT tools, or digital platforms in EE delivery. This indicates a significant gap and a potential area for scaling innovative approaches in EE.

Global Scan and Ecosystem Mapping

This component focused on mapping the current landscape of EE in secondary schools across Kenya and Rwanda, identifying both in-school and co-curricular practices. It also examined global best practices and innovative EE delivery models that offer potential for adaptation in the East African context. In addition, the study mapped key ecosystem actors and organizational typologies within the two countries, highlighting their roles, areas of specialization, and geographic reach. This analysis serves to inform program design and strategic engagement for EE actors and partners.

Approach

The global and regional ecosystem mapping of EE was conducted through a structured methodology combining desk-based reviews and typological classification using an evidence-based extraction framework. Specifically, the approach involved:

- **Desktop Review and Global Benchmarking:** A targeted scan of global EE platforms and toolkits was undertaken to identify best practices, especially those incorporating scalable, AI-enabled, or cost-effective delivery models.
- **EE Landscape Mapping in Kenya and Rwanda:** The mapping of national EE organizations in both countries was guided by a detailed extraction focus lens covering:
 - **Program Metadata:** Including country, program name, establishment date, and duration.

- **Institutional Typology:** Organization type (e.g., NGO, private sector, government), technical specialization (e.g., agribusiness, STEM, ICT), and geographic scope (e.g., urban, rural, national).
- **Target Groups:** Such as in-school youth, out-of-school youth, and educators.
- **Core Program Features:** Including key activities, pedagogy, curriculum models (didactics), funding mechanisms, and delivery modalities.
- **Technological Integration:** Use of technology and how digital tools (e.g., mobile, gamified platforms) are applied to enhance EE.
- **Alignment and Impact:** Program alignment with national EE policies, reported results, and perceived opportunities/challenges.
- **Sustainability and Scalability:** Financing models, long-term viability strategies, and institutional embedding of EE practices.
- **Typological Classification:** Organizations and initiatives were analyzed and grouped according to thematic dimensions such as:
 - **Program Intent and Pedagogy:** Differentiating between experiential, vocational, gamified, or life-skill-focused approaches.
 - **Implementation Strategies:** Differentiating co-curricular clubs, teacher training, digital learning, and industry partnerships.
 - **Impact Orientation:** Capturing behavioral outcomes (e.g., business formation), self-efficacy, and academic trade-offs.

Key Outputs

The mapping generated EE programs across Kenya and Rwanda, alongside a benchmarking of global best practices to contextualize local efforts and inform adaptive learning models.

Key outputs include:

- **A Typology of EE Programs in Kenya and Rwanda:** Seventeen (17) initiatives were mapped and categorized based on their duration, delivery format (curricular vs. co-curricular), target groups, funding models, and pedagogical approaches (see section findings)
- **Synthesis of Program Characteristics and Trends:** The mapping identified common objectives (e.g., entrepreneurial mindset development), delivery methods (e.g., experiential and hybrid learning), and thematic patterns in challenges and opportunities (e.g., digital access, teacher capacity, scalability).
- **Benchmarking of Global EE Platforms:** A range of global entrepreneurship education platforms were reviewed to assess their operations and map best practices as insights for the African context. These platforms primarily focused on secondary education and featured delivery models such as gamified learning, SMS-based communication, and AI-driven content. Key themes included startup creation, employability, experiential learning, teacher development, and strong public-private partnerships—offering valuable lessons for local adaptation in Kenya, Rwanda, and similar settings.
- **Online Scan of Global Best Practices:** Programs were profiled based on key design attributes (e.g., experiential learning, teacher development, scalable delivery), outcomes (e.g., capability building, startup creation), and their lessons for local adaptation—particularly for initiatives like Wavumbuzi. Emphasis was placed on inclusive design, context-driven content, and digital models suited for low-resource environments.

Section three | Findings

Introduction

This section presents the core findings of the study, drawn from the three distinct research components: bibliometric analysis, SLR, and ecosystem/platform mapping. The insights are organized thematically to reflect global patterns, national landscapes, and ecosystem-level dynamics in Kenya and Rwanda.

Global Best Practices & Innovation Trends *(from Bibliometric Analysis)*

Global Map: Entrepreneurship Education Landscape

A total number of 552 documents were used for the analysis of the global map below. It highlights significant disparities in the institutionalisation of EE at secondary school-level across countries.

Figure 1:
Global Map of
Entrepreneurship Education
in secondary schools

The global map illustrates varying levels of EE integration:

- **Dark blue regions** represent countries with the most developed EE systems, including the United States, China, South Korea, and parts of Western Europe. These countries have successfully embedded EE into national education policies and economic strategies. For example, the U.S. incorporates programs like NFTE and Junior Achievement into school curricula.
- **Medium blue regions** denote countries with expanding EE programs, often linked to innovation and youth employment agendas.
- **Light blue regions** highlight countries with early-stage or pilot EE initiatives, such as Kenya and Rwanda.
- **Grey regions** lack bibliometric evidence of EE activity at the secondary school-level, indicating either limited documentation or minimal program implementation.

In **Rwanda** and **Kenya**, the adoption of Competency-Based Curricula (CBC) has embedded entrepreneurship as a key competency aimed at fostering creativity, innovation, and practical problem-solving among secondary learners. In both countries, EE is conceptualized as a combination of a standalone subject and a cross-cutting skill, delivered through project-based and experiential learning approaches.

Rwanda has made notable progress through multi-stakeholder engagement, blending government efforts with civil society and NGO-led interventions. Programs such as Educate, *Akazi Kanoze*, *Junior Achievement Rwanda*, and *Wavumbuzi Rwanda* have introduced structured training, mentorship, and entrepreneurial simulations in secondary schools.

In Kenya, EE has been advanced through initiatives like *Junior Achievement Kenya*, *Wavumbuzi Kenya*, *Ajira Digital*, and partnerships with *Digital Opportunity Trust* and the *Young African Leaders Initiative (YALI)*. These programs focus on expanding access to EE, particularly through digital skills development and entrepreneurial upskilling.

Most Cited Countries in EE Literature

The graph below shows a bibliometric analysis of the 10 most cited countries in Entrepreneurship education in secondary schools.

Figure 2: Most cited Countries in the Globe

The citation analysis reveals that the United States leads globally in Entrepreneurship Education (EE) scholarship, with 3,352 total citations and an average of 25 citations per article. This underscores the U.S.'s pivotal role in shaping global EE discourse through its focus on experiential pedagogy, program scalability, and robust policy integration.

China ranks second with 1,683 citations, reflecting substantial investment in EE across all education levels, including secondary schools. However, its lower average citation per article (7.8) suggests that while the volume of Chinese EE research is high, global scholarly visibility may be constrained by language and publication access barriers.

European countries such as the Netherlands and Sweden demonstrate exceptionally high research impact, with average citations per article of 139.5 and 92.2, respectively. These countries exemplify advanced EE integration through progressive pedagogies—such as phenomenon-based learning, interdisciplinary projects, and social entrepreneurship challenges—embedded within their national curricula.

Other notable contributors include Germany, England, Australia, and Spain, which all feature in the top 10 citation rankings. Their EE strategies often link entrepreneurship to both economic empowerment and citizenship education, fostering creativity, collaboration, and real-world problem-solving in school-based projects.

While Kenya and Rwanda do not appear among the top 10 cited countries, their inclusion in the bibliometric dataset signals an emerging scholarly presence. Both countries are actively embedding EE into secondary school systems through policy reforms and innovative programming, and their visibility in global research is steadily increasing.

Global Keyword Occurrence of Entrepreneurship Education

The global keyword occurrence figure below shows the synthesis of keyword occurrences and the focused areas in EE in secondary schools across the globe.

Figure 3: Global keyword occurrence of Entrepreneurship Education

The keyword co-occurrence map places "students" at the center of the global EE discourse, affirming the primacy of learners in shaping and benefiting from entrepreneurship education. While clusters around terms like "colleges and universities" and "engineering education" signal a continued dominance of tertiary-level research, the appearance of keywords such as "curricula," "entrepreneurial skills," and "teaching" reflects a growing relevance to secondary school contexts.

The green cluster emphasizes EE's integration into practical disciplines like agriculture, business, and ICT, aligning closely with Kenya and Rwanda's competency-based curriculum reforms. Moreover, the adoption of digital simulation tools such as *SimVenture*, *GoVenture*, and *Mighty Networks*—traditionally confined to tertiary settings—is now expanding into tech-enabled secondary classrooms, signalling a downward diffusion of innovation-oriented pedagogy.

The orange cluster anchored around "entrepreneurship education" is closely connected to terms like pedagogy, entrepreneurial learning, and education reform. This reflects a regional alignment with the global trend toward experiential, student-centered learning, particularly at the adolescent level. The emphasis is shifting away from theoretical content delivery toward practical, action-oriented EE experiences, reinforcing learner autonomy and real-world application.

The green and blue clusters underscore the link between EE and broader economic development objectives particularly employment, self-employment, livelihoods, and agribusiness. These themes are especially relevant in rural and underserved contexts, where EE is deployed as a poverty alleviation tool and a means of youth empowerment. In Kenya, for example, agripreneurship initiatives have emerged in schools; however, they often suffer from tokenistic implementation, with agriculture treated as a low-priority elective lacking practical exposure and investment.

The yellow cluster reflects an emerging but critical shift towards digital entrepreneurship and empirical evaluation. Keywords like soft skills, online learning, and randomized controlled trials suggest that both Kenya and Rwanda are exploring innovative delivery methods and impact measurement frameworks. Programs such as the Wavumbuzi Entrepreneurship Challenge, which leverages mobile platforms to engage youth in entrepreneurship, show that digital EE is feasible even in low-resource settings and is gaining traction. However, notable gaps persist. Despite growing innovation, evaluation mechanisms remain weak, with limited longitudinal studies on EE's outcomes. Additionally, the presence of keywords like NGOs and education reform point to the dominance of donor-led interventions, raising concerns about program sustainability and ownership. Without stronger localization, full integration into teacher training systems, and systemic alignment, ongoing national efforts and government investment in EE risk remaining peripheral rather than transformative across both education systems.

National EE Landscape in Kenya and Rwanda (from the SLR)

Overview of Reviewed Studies

The analysis of the **23 selected studies that met the selection criteria** presents the following results:

- **Publication Years:** The studies were published between 2015 and 2024. The highest number of publications was recorded in 2022 (6 articles). There were no publications in 2017, while most other years recorded between 1 and 3 articles. The years 2023 and 2024 each had 2 publications.
- **Methodological Approaches:** Most of the studies (12) employed qualitative methodologies. Mixed methods and randomized controlled trials (RCTs) were each used in 4 studies. One study was classified as a policy document.
- **Geographic Focus:** Rwanda was the most common country of focus, with 14 studies, followed by Kenya with 7 studies. One study had a global scope (including Rwanda), and one had a Pan-African focus including Kenya.

Figure 7:
Trends in Methodologies and
Publication Years of Reviewed
Literature

Distribution of Articles by Country/Region Focus

Figure 8:
Distribution of Articles
by Country/Region Focus

Thematic Synthesis of Key Findings

The reviewed studies reveal recurring patterns across multiple dimensions of entrepreneurship education in Kenya and Rwanda. The following ten findings summarize key themes related to curriculum integration, teaching methods, program outcomes, funding, and system-level challenges.

- **Integration of EE into Competency-Based Curricula (CBC):** Both Kenya and Rwanda have formally integrated entrepreneurship education into their national CBC frameworks. Rwanda applies a cross-cutting approach, embedding EE across multiple subjects and education levels. Kenya introduces EE mainly through Business Studies and Life Skills. Despite policy-level integration, variations persist in implementation fidelity across regions and school types.
- **Impact and Outcomes of EE Programs:** The review highlights mixed but largely promising outcomes of EE programs. Studies in Rwanda demonstrate that gamified online courses and intensive teacher training positively influence student business activity and self-confidence. Practice-based learning approaches improve entrepreneurial intentions and soft skills. However, some interventions show minimal impact on academic performance or entrepreneurial mindset, particularly when lacking follow-up or contextual relevance.

- **Curriculum Design and Inclusivity:** While CBC frameworks champion learner-centered and inclusive education, implementation gaps persist:
 - Gender sensitivity is limited with few programs tailored for girls' specific needs or challenges.
 - Learners with disabilities remain underserved due to lack of adaptive materials and infrastructure.
 - Local contextualization of curriculum content is weak, often failing to align with community realities or entrepreneurial opportunities.
 - Out-of-school youth, a high-need segment, are insufficiently targeted by current EE efforts.
- **Pedagogical Approaches and Instructional Models:** Innovative instructional models such as experiential learning, dialogic instruction, gamified learning, and project-based education are associated with higher engagement, entrepreneurial self-efficacy, and real-world skills acquisition. EE clubs and school-led ventures have shown success in fostering student entrepreneurship behavior. However, the absence of strong mentorship networks and industry linkages remains a common shortfall. Traditional rote-based teaching continues to dominate many classrooms, undermining EE's experiential potential.
- **Role of Technology in Entrepreneurship Education:** Digital tools such as gamified platforms enhanced EE delivery, especially in urban areas. These tools were associated with improved entrepreneurial behaviors, club participation, and weekly earnings. The digital divide remained a barrier in rural settings. Informal digital entrepreneurship was commonly observed among Kenyan youth.
- **Funding and Resource Mobilization:** EE programs were generally underfunded. Many successful co-curricular initiatives relied on external donor support. Specific needs reported included:
 - Dedicated funding for teacher training and EE materials
 - Investment in digital infrastructure
 - Support for learner entrepreneurship ventures through microgrants
 - Exploration of community-based financing and microfinance models
- **Sustainability and Scalability of EE Initiatives:** Most EE programs had not moved beyond pilot phases and remained concentrated in a few schools. Barriers to scale included:
 - Limited local capacity to expand initiatives
 - Weak alignment with school systems
 - Lack of follow-up mechanisms for learner outcomes
- **Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E):** M&E frameworks for EE were underdeveloped. Programs lacked:
 - Standardized indicators to track entrepreneurial competencies
 - Tools to assess long-term outcomes
 - Data systems for continuous improvement
- **Persistent Systemic Challenges:** Several structural barriers were consistently observed:
 - Inadequate teacher preparation in EE methods
 - Dominance of traditional teaching styles (lack of pedagogical innovation)
 - Insufficient physical and digital infrastructure, especially in rural schools
- **Policy Alignment and Implementation Gaps:** National policies such as Kenya Vision 2030 and Rwanda Vision 2050 emphasize EE, and more can be done to enhance implementation. Studies identified:
 - Inadequate funding for EE execution
 - Weak coordination among government and private actors
 - Lack of operational M&E systems at policy level

Ecosystem Actors and Program Typologies (from Platform Mapping)

Overview of EE Landscape

A total of 17 EE programs were reviewed across Kenya and Rwanda, spanning the period from 1999 to 2025. Rwanda hosts 9 initiatives, while Kenya accounts for 8. The programs vary in duration, from as short as 6 weeks to as long as 4 years. Most of the initiatives (14 out of 17) operate as co-curricular programs, and only 3 are embedded within school curricula.

Figure 9: EE Initiative Trends: Establishment Years and Program Lengths

Figure 10: EE Initiatives by Country and Program Type: A Comparative Overview

Target Groups and Reach

Secondary students are the primary target group (11/17 programs). Other groups include female students, teachers, and mixed cohorts such as TVET learners and teacher-student pairs. Two programs target teachers and students simultaneously, enhancing cross-stakeholder engagement.

Figure 11: Target Groups and Reach of EE Programmes

Pedagogical and Delivery Models

Experiential learning is the most common pedagogy, often combined with mentorship or teamwork. Hybrid delivery models (blending online and physical) are the most frequently used didactic approach, followed by purely physical formats.

Figure 12: Pedagogical and Delivery Models of EE Programmes

Program Objectives and Outcomes

Most initiatives (13/17) aim to cultivate entrepreneurial mindset and skills. Two programs target teacher development, while one each addresses business creation and female empowerment. Outcomes range from entrepreneurial skill acquisition (12/17) to startup creation and curriculum development.

Figure 13: Objectives and Outcomes of Entrepreneurship Education Initiatives

Implementation of Activities and Technology Integration in EE Programs

Most programs adopt hybrid models such as Practicum + Lecture or Practicum + Competition, combining theoretical and experiential learning. Additional approaches include mentorship, incubation, and peer collaboration. Lectures are used in 6 programs, while 5 incorporate competitive elements. Technology integration is predominantly moderate, with 10 out of 17 programs utilizing digital tools for learning, mentorship, and competitions. Notably, Wavumbuzi stands out for its fully digital, gamified platform. However, challenges such as digital access disparities and limited infrastructure continue to hinder scalability.

Key Activities and Technology Use in EE Programs

Figure 14:
Activities and Technology
Integration in Entrepreneurship
Education (EE) Programs

Financing, Funders, and Sustainability

The analysis shows that NGOs are the primary funders of EE initiatives, supporting 12 out of the reviewed programs. Public-private partnerships (PPPs) fund 3 initiatives, while government support is observed in only 2. In terms of sustainability, key strategies include integration into education policy and engagement with PPPs (each reported in 4 programs). Additional approaches involve leveraging alumni networks and implementing recurring models at the local level (3 programs each). However, most initiatives still exhibit a high level of donor dependence, indicating a need for more robust and diversified funding models.

Figure 15:
Financing, Funders, and
Sustainability Strategies of EE
Initiatives

Challenges and Opportunities in EE Implementation

The most cited implementation challenge across EE initiatives is the combination of resource constraints, teacher readiness gaps, and scalability issues (noted in 5 programs). Other recurring challenges include digital access inequities (2 programs) and issues such as limited funding consistency, club activity variability, and gender-related barriers—all reported in at least one initiative.

Despite these obstacles, several growth and innovation opportunities were identified. Scalability remains the most emphasized opportunity, highlighted in 9 programs. Digital expansion follows closely, mentioned in 4 initiatives. Other avenues for growth include government co-sponsorship, private sector investment, industry linkages, and technology-driven rural scaling—each cited once.

Figure 16: Implementation Challenges and Innovation Opportunities in EE Initiatives

Benchmarking of Global EE Platforms

• Impact and Target Level

The analysis of global EE platforms revealed that Startup Creation and Employability emerged as the most common program impact, followed by Capability Building and Entrepreneurial Activation. Other areas such as Skill Development and Networking and Financial Literacy and Inclusion were addressed in fewer initiatives.

Regarding target audience, Secondary Education was the predominant focus across the platforms. A few initiatives extended their reach to Primary Education, Tertiary Education, and programs that spanned multiple education levels (e.g., primary, secondary, and tertiary). This highlights a global emphasis on integrating EE at the secondary level to build entrepreneurial capacity early in learners' educational journeys.

Figure 17: Program Outcomes and Targeted Educational Levels in EE Initiatives

- **Best Practices in Global EE Program Design**

The success of global EE programs is anchored in practices such as Experiential Learning, Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs), Teacher Development, Blended Learning with Industry Collaboration, Student-Led and Team-Based Initiatives, Leadership and Vocational Integration, STEM inclusion, and scalable digital delivery. These approaches reflect a growing international emphasis on real-world, inclusive, and multi-stakeholder learning models.

For Kenya and Rwanda, key lessons include enhancing technology use, empowering teachers for sustainable delivery, embedding entrepreneurship in formal curricula, and promoting early exposure and foundational skills. Other strategies include community engagement, mentorship through competitions and practical activities, digital learning models to support scale, and designing adaptive, inclusive programs tailored to underserved populations. Strong mechanisms for monitoring, sustainability, and replicability are also essential.

- **Analysis of Global EE Platforms**

The analysis (see Table 1) and evaluation area of global EE platforms highlight several delivery models, strengths, and areas for improvement.

Area	Design Element of the Reviewed Platforms	
Program Design and Delivery Approaches	Most platforms utilize immersive and gamified models, often supplemented by SMS-based solutions for low-connectivity areas. These approaches align with simulation-based, adaptive, and curriculum-aligned designs, fostering personalized and engaging experiences.	
Technology Integration and Platform Strengths	Technology is strategically applied to promote deep skill acquisition, interpersonal development, and personalized learning. Best practices emphasize adaptive, feedback-driven, and context-aware learning environments.	
Outcomes and Impact	Prioritize nurturing real-world problem-solving and lifelong learning, with key outcomes including capability building and entrepreneurial activation (e.g., startup creation, employability).	
Offline Accessibility	Allow for offline functionality to significantly improve access for learners without consistent internet connectivity.	

Table 1: Analysis of global EE platforms and their design elements

Comprehensiveness	Adopt a holistic EE approach, seamlessly integrating social-emotional learning (SEL) alongside entrepreneurial mastery.
Collaboration and Community Building	Actively promote collaboration and foster a sense of community among learners and mentors.
Context Sensitivity	Develop context-driven and locally relevant content, ensuring that learning materials resonate with the specific needs and realities of the target audience.
Feedback and Adaptivity	A strong emphasis is placed on feedback-driven, personalized, and adaptive learning mechanisms to cater to individual learner paces and needs.

Figure 18:
Instructional Design,
Technology Integration,
and Impact Dimensions of
Benchmarked Global EE
Platforms Comparable to
Wavumbuzi

Section four | Discussion

Synthesis Across the Three Components

The findings from the Bibliometric Analysis, SLR, and Global Scan reveal a multidimensional understanding of the Entrepreneurship Education (EE) landscape in secondary schools across Kenya and Rwanda. Each research component contributes unique insights:

- The **Bibliometric Analysis** positioned Kenya and Rwanda within the global EE discourse, revealing limited African authorship and underrepresentation of secondary school contexts in international scholarship.
- The **SLR** mapped current EE programs, highlighted implementation barriers, and emphasized the gap between curriculum intentions and delivery practices.
- The **Global Scan and Ecosystem Mapping** showcased promising innovations, including AI-based and gamified EE platforms, while identifying fragmented delivery models and uneven geographical coverage of EE programs.

Collectively, these insights present a comprehensive baseline for identifying where systemic improvement and strategic investments are needed.

Thematic Synthesis of EE Insights

This section integrates findings from the bibliometric analysis, systematic literature review (SLR), and global scan to present a synthesized view of the EE landscape in Kenya and Rwanda. The insights are grouped into three thematic clusters for easy discussion: (i) Knowledge and Curriculum, (ii) Delivery and Access, and (iii) Systemic Support and Ecosystem Strengthening.

Knowledge and Curriculum

- **Positioning in Global EE Discourse and Research Gaps**

Both Rwanda and Kenya have embedded entrepreneurship into their **Competency-Based Curricula (CBC)** as a core or cross-cutting subject designed to equip learners with entrepreneurial knowledge, creativity, and problem-solving competencies.

The mode of EE delivery remains uneven across rural and urban schools. Even though there are innovative digital efforts, structural inequities hinder equitable access and pedagogical effectiveness.

- **Curriculum Integration and Delivery Practices**

The integration of EE into the CBC frameworks in both Kenya and Rwanda reflects a positive policy shift toward equipping learners with entrepreneurial mindsets and skills from an early age. However, the observed variation in how these curricula frameworks are interpreted and delivered at the school-level suggests that policy alone is insufficient to guarantee effective implementation. The segmented approach in Kenya and the cross-cutting model in Rwanda each offer distinct strengths, yet both face challenges in translating curriculum intent into consistent classroom practice. This underscores the importance of aligning curriculum design with contextual realities such as teacher preparedness, school infrastructure, and learner diversity. Strengthening curriculum delivery will require clearer implementation guidelines, targeted teacher support, and greater linkage between formal curricula and the growing ecosystem of co-curricular entrepreneurship initiatives.

Delivery and Access

- **Innovative Pedagogies and Technology Use**

The growing use of adaptive AI driven, gamification, and simulation in global EE platforms highlights a shift toward learner-centered and adaptive pedagogies. However, EE delivery in Kenya and Rwanda remains largely lecture-based, teacher-centered, and focused on memorization rather than hands-on learning or learner participation, limiting learner engagement and practical skill development. This contrast reveals an opportunity to localize proven digital tools and experiential models to suit local contexts. Leveraging platforms like Wavumbuzi and aligning pedagogy with digital behavior could enhance relevance and inclusivity in EE. Scaling such innovations will require investment in teacher digital capacity, infrastructure, and contextual content adaptation.

- **Equity and Inclusion in Access to EE**

Despite growing recognition of the need for inclusive entrepreneurship education, disparities remain pronounced across geography, gender, disability, and socio-economic status. Learners in rural and under-resourced areas face limited access to trained teachers, learning materials, and digital infrastructure. Girls and learners with disabilities are often overlooked due to a lack of tailored pedagogies and support systems. Out-of-school youth, though a high-need segment, remain largely excluded from formal EE programs. Addressing these gaps will require targeted interventions that prioritize access, affordability, and relevance—particularly in resource-constrained settings.

- **Teacher Capacity and Professional Development**

The effectiveness of EE delivery is closely tied to teacher competence and confidence in entrepreneurial pedagogy. However, findings indicate that many teachers lack adequate training in both content and methodology, with limited access to continuous professional development (CPD) opportunities. Most EE-related training remains short-term, donor-driven, and not systematically embedded in national teacher development frameworks. As a result, pedagogical readiness varies widely across schools and regions. Strengthening teacher capacity will require long-term investment in EE-specific training, practical exposure to entrepreneurship, and integration of EE into pre-service and in-service teacher education programs.

Systemic Support and Ecosystem Strengthening

- **Ecosystem Composition and Coordination Challenges**

The EE ecosystem in Kenya and Rwanda is composed of a wide range of actors, including government agencies, NGOs, public-private partnerships (PPPs), EdTech providers, donors, and community-based organizations. While this diversity reflects strong interest in EE, few mechanisms exist to standardize approaches, share data, or align activities with government priorities. Strengthening ecosystem coordination will require shared frameworks, clearer role definition, and structured platforms for collaboration across sectors.

- **Program Funding, Sustainability, and Scalability**

Most EE programs in Kenya and Rwanda rely heavily on external donor support, with limited long-term financing from domestic sources. This funding model often constrains sustainability, as programs face uncertainty once donor cycles end. Few initiatives have built-in mechanisms for financial continuity, such as integration into government budgets or income-generating components. Scalability is also hindered by capacity limitations at the local level, lack of institutional ownership, and the absence of standard operating models. These gaps highlight the need for diversified funding strategies and frameworks that support long-term institutionalization and broader program reach.

- **Monitoring, Evaluation, and Data Gaps**

Entrepreneurship Education programs across Kenya and Rwanda face significant gaps in monitoring and evaluation (M&E). Most lack standardized indicators, robust data systems, or tools to track learner outcomes over time. This limits the ability of implementers and policymakers to assess program effectiveness, adapt interventions, or scale what works. The absence of feedback loops means programs rarely benefit from evidence-based refinement or cross-learning. Strengthening M&E will require context-appropriate frameworks, integration into national education data systems, and routine use of findings to inform planning and resource allocation.

- **Policy-Practice Bridging**

While national policies in both Kenya and Rwanda articulate strong commitments to entrepreneurship education, opportunity for enhancements and improvements remain between these strategies and their execution at the school level. While many schools lack the resources, capacity, or guidance needed to implement EE as envisioned in policy frameworks, these opportunities can improve well-intentioned policies and reinforce consistencies in EE delivery. Applying these enhancements will require stronger policy translation mechanisms, adequate financing, and clearer implementation pathways.

- **Emerging Opportunities for Contextual Innovation**

Despite systemic challenges, several promising opportunities are emerging to strengthen entrepreneurship education in contextually relevant ways. Informal digital entrepreneurship—particularly among youth using mobile platforms and social media—demonstrates untapped potential for aligning EE with learners' lived experiences. Community-based co-funding models and school-level microgrants offer practical entry points for supporting learner-led ventures. Hybrid learning approaches that blend digital tools with in-person mentorship are also gaining traction, especially where infrastructure allows. Peer-led mentoring, student clubs, and localized content development present further avenues for embedding EE within everyday school environments. Leveraging these innovations will require flexible, inclusive models that respond to diverse learning contexts across Kenya and Rwanda.

Gaps and Opportunities

Gaps Identified

- Limited use of technology and innovative pedagogies in EE delivery.
- Insufficient teacher training tailored to entrepreneurship content and methodology.
- Weak monitoring and evaluation systems across programs.
- Underrepresentation of locally authored, implementation-focused research.
- Inadequate inclusion of learners from under-resourced backgrounds, especially out-of-school youth and those with disabilities.

Strategic Opportunities

- **Introduce low-cost, tech-enabled EE platforms** in partnership with EdTech providers.
- **Support locally led research and policy dialogues** to elevate African perspectives in EE.
- **Convene cross-sectoral coalitions** to align EE efforts with national and regional development agendas.
- **Invest in contextualized teacher development** and toolkits adaptable to resource-constrained environments.
- **Leverage informal entrepreneurship trends and hybrid learning** models (e.g., mobile-first, social media, peer-led mentoring) to reach learners outside traditional school systems.
- **Expand co-curricular EE delivery** through student clubs, competitions, and school-led enterprises to complement formal instruction.
- **Explore community-based financing models** (e.g., school-level microgrants, co-funding) to enhance sustainability and local ownership.

Section five | Recommendations

Introduction

Based on the findings and cross-analysis of the EE landscape, this section presents targeted policy and programmatic recommendations for four key stakeholder groups: Governments and Implementing Partners, Schools and Teacher Training Institutions, and Donors and Ecosystem Enablers. These recommendations are designed to address the systemic and programmatic gaps identified in the previous sections, and aim to enhance the quality, inclusivity, coordination, and overall impact of EE in secondary schools in Kenya and Rwanda. Grounded in global best practices and aligned with ecosystem building missions, the proposed actions are adapted to local contexts and national ambitions under the Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC) and long-term development frameworks such as Vision 2030 and Vision 2050.

For Governments of Kenya and Rwanda

Governments are key to embedding and sustaining EE. The following actions focus on policy, training, infrastructure, and system coordination.

- **Strengthen National Policy Frameworks:** Ensure that EE is embedded in education sector policies, youth employment strategies, and national development plans, with operational guidelines and budgetary commitments.
- **Institutionalize Entrepreneurship in Pre-Service & In-Service Teacher Training:** Introduce EE pedagogy training in teacher colleges and develop CPD modules focused on experiential, learner-centered approaches and real-world application.
- **Improve Infrastructure and Digital Access:** Continue investing in ICT infrastructure (electricity, devices, and connectivity), particularly in rural and under-served schools, to enable inclusive access to digital EE platforms and innovative learning.
- **Develop a Centralized EE Monitoring & Evaluation System:** Establish national M&E frameworks with clear indicators and integrate EE tracking into the Education Management Information System (EMIS).
- **Foster Coordination Among Key Actors:** Actively engage key ecosystem actors such as NGOs, development partners, and private sector stakeholders—to guide a harmonized, ecosystem-based approach to EE delivery.

For Implementing Partners

Implementing partners play a catalytic role in advancing inclusive, scalable EE models. The recommendations focus on innovation, collaboration, and evidence generation.

- **Support Localization of Global Best Practices:** Pilot and adapt digital, gamified, and AI-enabled adaptive EE models for local relevance, especially for learners in marginalized contexts.
- **Invest in Scalable Teacher Support Models:** Design low-cost toolkits, mentorship platforms, and EE communities of practice in partnership with TTCs and universities to ensure regional scalability and contextual fit.
- **Convene and Facilitate Multi-Stakeholder Platforms:** Leverage on convening power to align actors (government, NGOs, EdTech, research institutions) and promote joint programming, shared standards, and co-investment strategies.

- **Sponsor Locally-led EE Research:** Fund African researchers and institutions to generate implementation-focused insights on EE that reflect youth voice, local barriers, and context-specific solutions.
- **Develop a Regional EE Innovation Hub:** Establish a knowledge hub to incubate and scale context-relevant EE models, facilitate cross-border learning, and monitor emerging trends.

For Schools and Teacher Training Institutions

Development partners, philanthropic foundations, policy think tanks, and research networks can strengthen the EE ecosystem through long-term support, data-driven programs, and alignment with national strategies.

- **Integrate Practical EE Activities Across Subjects:** Embed entrepreneurship in science, arts, and social studies using school enterprises, project-based learning, and student competitions.
- **Foster School-Level Innovation Labs or Clubs:** Establish EE clubs or innovation spaces where learners can test ideas, build prototypes, and interact with mentors from the business community.
- **Strengthen Teacher Confidence in EE Delivery:** Equip teachers with practical exposure to entrepreneurship through exchange programs, local enterprise visits, and collaboration with real-world entrepreneurs.
- **Promote Gender-Inclusive and Accessible EE Approaches:** Support learners with disabilities by incorporating universal design and culturally relevant pedagogy.

For Donors and Ecosystem Enablers

(e.g., development partners, philanthropic foundations, policy think tanks, and research networks)

These actors can accelerate systemic change by aligning support with national priorities, investing in locally led solutions, and fostering coordination across the EE landscape.

- **Support Long-Term, Locally driven EE Programs:** Shift from short-term pilots to multi-year funding that prioritizes sustainability, government ownership, and local capacity building.
- **Encourage Evidence-Based Program Design:** Require funding recipients to embed research, M&E, and policy learning loops into their EE interventions.
- **Promote Ecosystem Mapping and Data Sharing:** Fund real-time EE ecosystem dashboards that track actors, activities, and opportunities to foster transparency and collaboration.
- **Align Support with National Education Strategies:** Ensure donor programs are not duplicative or isolated but complement and reinforce national priorities, CBC reforms, and Vision 2030/2050 frameworks.

Section six | Conclusion and Strategic Pathways

Conclusion

This report has provided a comprehensive overview of the Entrepreneurship Education (EE) landscape in secondary schools across Kenya and Rwanda, drawing from bibliometric analysis, systematic literature review, and ecosystem mapping.

However, the findings also highlight significant opportunities to strengthen EE as a transformative tool for youth empowerment and inclusive economic development. Addressing systemic barriers such as teacher capacity gaps, curriculum delivery inconsistencies, limited access to digital infrastructure, and weak inter-stakeholder coordination will be critical.

To unlock EE's full potential, this report calls for a coordinated, multi-stakeholder approach that is:

- Context-responsive and equity-driven,
- Grounded in evidence and innovation,
- Anchored in sustainability.

Strategic Pathways for Transformative Impact

The following pathways offer a practical roadmap for policy reform and action, aligned to national contexts and stakeholder mandates.

Table 2: Strategic Pathways for Advancing Entrepreneurship Education in Kenya, Rwanda, and the East African Region

Pathway	Kenya	Rwanda	Cross-Cutting Regional Policy Intervention	Cross-Cutting Regional Practitioner Intervention
Curriculum Reform & Integration	Consolidate EE modules into an integrated national framework aligned with CBC reforms.	Strengthen existing cross-cutting EE model with clearer classroom implementation guidelines.	Develop a regional EE curriculum playbook or toolkit adaptable across East Africa.	Embed practical EE projects into classroom activities and co-curricular programs.
Teacher Training & CPD	Develop national EE training modules embedded in TTCs and school-based CPD platforms.	Expand EE-focused CPD and in-service training.	Promote EE teacher exchange programs and communities of practice across borders.	Implement peer mentoring, practice-based teaching methods, and use real-world case studies.

Inclusive Access & Equity	Prioritize EE investment in ASALs, low-income counties, and special-needs schools.	Scale inclusive EE programs for girls and learners with disabilities.	Support regional digital inclusion strategies for out-of-school youth and remote learners.	Adapt teaching strategies to address diverse learner needs and promote inclusive participation.
Innovation & Technology	Localize and scale EdTech platforms.	Build national digital content aligned to EE, leveraging simulation and gamification.	Co-create open-source, multilingual EE tools with EdTech partners for regional use.	Pilot tech-enabled learning tools and experiential EE formats in diverse school settings.
Monitoring, Data & Evidence	Maintain and increase country engagement with national EE data dashboard.	Maintain and increase country engagement with national EE data dashboard.	Create a regional EE data dashboard and promote harmonized outcome tracking.	Utilize M&E tools to collect and reflect on learner progress and instructional impact.
Policy-Implementation Bridge			Facilitate regional policy dialogues and peer learning for governments and partners.	Engage in policy dialogue through teacher associations and share frontline implementation insights.
Funding & Sustainability	Embed EE programs in national education budgets and county development plans.	Mobilize blended financing (public-private) for long-term EE delivery.	Coordinate donor investment frameworks aligned to national and regional EE goals.	Leverage local partnerships to sustain EE clubs and income-generating school ventures.
Research & Thought Leadership	Fund locally led EE research and policy briefs through Kenyan think tanks and universities.	Support longitudinal EE impact studies led by Rwandan institutions.	Launch an East Africa EE Knowledge Hub hosted by AGGP EA or a research network.	Collaborate with researchers to document best practices and scale evidence-informed innovations.

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Introduction

This annexes section presents additional figures, tables, and comparative insights that support the report's findings.

PRISMA Flowcharts

PRISMA Flowchart for Bibliometric Analysis

The diagrams below show the PRISMA guidelines used for the African countries and combined Rwanda and Kenya bibliometric analysis conducted for the study.

Figure 19:
PRISMA guidelines for
African countries

PRISMA guidelines for Rwanda and Kenya

Figure 20:
PRISMA guidelines for
Rwanda and Kenya

A total number of 552 documents were used for the analysis of the global map below. The initial search showed 2667 documents; however, a further review of the documents excluded 976 documents as they were not written in English language and not journal articles. Upon a further review and limiting the documents to only the appropriate keyword search and final publication stage 702 documents were removed. Due to double duplication, keywords only appearing on abstract and some of the documents being not on the scope of the study a further 437 documents were removed.

PRISMA Flowchart: Systematic Literature Review (SLR)

This flowchart illustrates the step-by-step process followed in the Systematic Literature Review on Entrepreneurship Education (EE) in secondary schools in Kenya and Rwanda. The review applied the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) framework to ensure transparency and rigor. Records were sourced from ERIC, Scopus, Web of Science, and other academic databases, screened against inclusion and exclusion criteria, and reviewed for relevance and quality. Ultimately, 23 peer-reviewed studies published between 2015 and 2025 were retained for full analysis. The flowchart summarizes each stage of the search, screening, and selection process.

Figure 21: PRISMA Flowchart-Systematic Literature Review (SLR)

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for a Systematic Literature Review (SLR)

Table 3: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for a Systematic Literature Review (SLR)

Inclusion Criteria	
Criterion	Details
Geographic Focus	Studies conducted in or focused on Kenya and/or Rwanda
Thematic Focus	Entrepreneurship education, training programs, curriculum development, or skills promotion
Education Level	Targeted at secondary school-levels
Language	Published in English
Publication Type	Peer-reviewed journal articles, conference proceedings, working papers, and relevant grey literature
Publication Date Range	2015–2025 to capture recent and relevant developments
Methodological Rigor	Empirical (qualitative, quantitative, or mixed methods), conceptual or theoretical studies
Relevance to Policy or Practice	Studies that provide policy recommendations, evaluate programs, or describe interventions aimed at entrepreneurship education
Exclusion Criteria	
Criterion	Details
Outside Target Countries	Studies not focused on Kenya or Rwanda
Irrelevant Topics	Studies not related to entrepreneurship or education/training
Non-School Settings	Studies targeting only adult entrepreneurship, informal sector outside the formal education system
Non-Empirical	Opinion pieces, editorials, blog posts, or purely anecdotal work
Non-English Publications	Articles not available in English
Duplicates	Duplicate entries across databases or preprints later published in journals
Outdated Publications	Studies published before the defined cut-off year (pre-2015)

Data Protocol Template

To guide consistent and comprehensive analysis of the reviewed studies, a structured data protocol template was used. The template aligned with the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) objectives and enabled systematic documentation of study characteristics, intervention types, target groups, key findings, identified gaps, policy implications, and alignment with national strategies.

The data fields used for extraction are outlined below.

- Serial Number (SN)
- SLR Objective Area – e.g., (serialized objective e.g. 2 for Mapping EE landscape)
- Author(s) & Year
- Title of Article / Study
- Country / Region Focus
- Methodology – Qualitative, Quantitative, Mixed methods, RCT, Case Study, etc.
- Type of Intervention – Curriculum, Co-curricular program, Policy initiative, Pilot project, etc.
- Target Group – Students, Teachers, Policymakers, Administrators, etc.
- Summary of Key Findings – Focus on entrepreneurship education insights
- Identified Gaps – Curriculum design, teacher training, learning resources, inclusion, etc.
- Policy Relevance / Recommendations – Explicit suggestions or implications for national or school policy
- Technology Use – Mention of AI, ICT tools, digital platforms, EdTech integration
- Government Strategy Alignment – Whether the study references or aligns with national strategies (Yes/No + explanation)
- Source – Journal name, DOI, or database (Scopus, Web of Science, ERIC, etc.)
- Additional Notes – Study quality, limitations, contextual considerations, etc.

List of EE Organizations

Current EE Landscape in Rwanda and Kenya

This section presents a curated snapshot of leading EE programs currently active in secondary schools across Kenya and Rwanda. Each initiative reflects different approaches from curriculum integration and teacher training to digital competitions and gender- focused interventions.

Table 4: Current EE Landscape in Rwanda and Kenya

Organization name	Logo	Description
Rwanda Education Board		Rwanda Education Board launched the National EE Curriculum in 2020, this four-year initiative integrates entrepreneurship into the national Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC) for secondary students. It emphasizes experiential and project-based learning but faces challenges in teacher capacity and digital infrastructure. The curriculum is public sector-driven and offers a foundational policy framework for long-term integration.
Educate! Exchange		Established in 2016, this program enhances teacher capacity through mentorship and structured training. It equips teachers to deliver entrepreneurship content effectively, fostering student-centered instruction. The initiative is supported by donors and focuses on train-the-trainer models with moderate use of digital tools

<p>IDEA4Africa</p>		<p>Founded in 2014, this 6–12-month program offers hands-on entrepreneurship training for students and teachers. Activities include business incubation, project development, and startup coaching. While impactful in fostering entrepreneurial skills, sustainability depends on partnerships and external funding.</p>
<p>Wavumbuzi Challenge (Rwanda)</p>		<p>Launched in 2020, this six-week online gamified competition engages secondary learners in entrepreneurial mindset, problem-solving, and skills. Fully digital, the platform offers scalability and national reach, though access remains uneven in rural and low-income areas.</p>
<p>JA Rwanda</p>		<p>started in 2019, JA Rwanda targets female secondary students, delivering experiential learning and mentorship. The program builds work readiness and confidence among girls. It leverages digital platforms for learning and mentorship, and collaborates closely with government institutions.</p>
<p>Akazi Kanoze Access (AKA)</p>		<p>Operating since 2009, AKA provides both theoretical and experiential content focused on work readiness and entrepreneurial thinking. The blended delivery model includes digital training and mentorship. Challenges remain around funding and teacher preparedness.</p>
<p>School Entrepreneurship Network (SEN)</p>		<p>Since 2011, SEN has operated as a one-year extracurricular program involving competitions and experiential activities for secondary learners. It promotes an entrepreneurial mindset through challenges and clubs. Despite donor support, activity levels vary across schools, and digital adoption remains minimal. Founded in 2014, this competition promotes innovation and entrepreneurship among girls in ICT. It uses online platforms for mentoring and idea pitching. The program fosters leadership and tech-driven skills but faces gender stereotyping and resource challenges.</p>
<p>Prince's Trust International – "Enterprise Challenge"</p>		<p>This short-term (3–6 months) competition-based initiative, active since 2015, encourages students to apply business ideas in real-world scenarios. Delivered in partnership with corporate sponsors, it promotes creativity and teamwork, though nationwide scalability is limited by training constraints.</p>

Organization name	Logo	Description
The Government of Kenya		The Government of Kenya implemented the Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC) in 2017, CBC embeds EE in the national curriculum, promoting active and experiential learning. However, rollout is uneven, and access to resources and trained educators remains a challenge.
Dajara-Transition Program active		Dajara-Transition Program active since 2013, this four-month blended program supports students with theoretical training and experiential projects. Alumni networks and partnerships enhance its reach, though resource constraints limit consistent delivery.
Asante Africa LEI		Asante Africa LEI running since 2006, the Leadership and Entrepreneurship Incubator equips students with life and entrepreneurial skills using peer evaluation and simulations. It is delivered in both in-person and digital formats, targeting underserved learners.
LaunchX AwardX East Africa		Initiated in 2012, this program blends competitive challenges and mentorship to foster real-world entrepreneurial practice. Its structure promotes peer learning, though some younger participants struggle with the technical rigor.
Tunapanda Institute		Founded in 2013, Tunapanda provides project-based training for disadvantaged youth. Combining digital learning with mentorship, it addresses entrepreneurship and digital literacy. Scaling remains limited by funding and infrastructure.
Kenya Startup School – Educator Module		Kenya Startup School – Educator Module Launching in 2025, this initiative trains educators to deliver EE using a blend of theory and experiential activities. It aligns with national policy and uses digital platforms for training and mentorship. The program seeks to address gaps in teacher preparation and curriculum delivery.

JA Kenya		JA Kenya was established in 1999. JA Kenya uses competitions, simulations, and mentorship to develop entrepreneurial skills. It works in partnership with public and private sectors and supports startups among youth through experiential programming.
Wavumbuzi Challenge (Kenya)		Launched in 2019, this six-week online gamified competition engages secondary learners in entrepreneurial mindset, problem-solving and skills. Fully digital, the platform offers scalability and national reach, though access remains uneven in rural and low-income areas.

Global Best Practices in Entrepreneurship Education Programs

Globally, several high-impact EE programs have emerged that offer valuable lessons for Kenya and Rwanda's secondary education sectors. These case studies were selected because they exemplify diverse, high-impact approaches to entrepreneurship education across different contexts. They align with OECD criteria by offering strong curriculum integration, experiential learning, teacher support, and ecosystem collaboration. Several use technologies, and demonstrate scalability, inclusivity, and adaptability making them highly relevant for informing EE strategies in Kenya and Rwanda's secondary school systems.

Table 5: Global Best Practices in Entrepreneurship Education Programs

Organization name	Logo	Description
JA Company Program		It provides students with immersive, real-world business experiences. Learners create and run simulated companies, engaging in marketing, finance, and operations. The programs emphasize learning-by-doing, supported by mentorship and, increasingly, digital tools. Their success in fostering entrepreneurial thinking and soft skills makes them highly adaptable for integration into East African curricula.
European Young Enterprise (EYE)		EYE demonstrates the value of a longitudinal entrepreneurship education pipeline—spanning from primary to tertiary education. It underscores the impact of early and sustained exposure to entrepreneurial skills and values, which is essential in shaping future-ready learners.
NFTE		NFTE delivers a structured, project-based curriculum that builds core entrepreneurial competencies—opportunity recognition, problem-solving, business planning, and pitching. Its emphasis on innovation and real-world application offers a replicable model for experiential entrepreneurship education in Africa, particularly in urban and under-resourced settings.

Team Academy		<p>Even though aimed at higher education, Team Academy's team-based, project-led learning model is widely recognized for fostering initiative, responsibility, and problem-solving. Its principles can inform the design of upper-secondary EE programs that prioritize real-world learning and student ownership.</p>
Young Enterprise		<p>These programs engage students in business competitions and team challenges where they ideate, launch, and manage businesses. The strong focus on teamwork, creativity, and digital fluency equips students with practical and transferable skills. Such initiatives align well with competency-based education reforms in Kenya and Rwanda.</p>
School Enterprise Challenge		<p>This global initiative empowers students to create and operate sustainable, school-based businesses. It encourages creativity, leadership, and practical financial management. Its flexible, scalable model and alignment with real community needs make it especially applicable in rural and peri-urban African schools.</p>
Young Achievement Australia (YAA)		<p>YAA's programs place secondary learners in team-run business simulations, building leadership, innovation, and communication skills. Their success in improving learners' confidence and enterprise awareness offers useful design features for local adaptation.</p>
BizWorld		<p>BizWorld introduces entrepreneurship through interactive, story-driven projects at the primary and lower secondary levels. It fosters teamwork, budgeting, and decision-making, serving as an effective early foundation for entrepreneurial thinking that can be scaled upward in education systems.</p>
INJAZ / JA Arabia		<p>INJAZ adapts global EE models to local contexts across the Middle East and North Africa. Through experiential learning, financial literacy, and mentorship, students gain work-readiness and entrepreneurship skills. The program's flexibility and emphasis on relevance to local economies make it a strong reference point for adaptation in Sub-Saharan Africa.</p>

<p>Society of Entrepreneurs (SOE) Singapore</p>		<p>Student Entrepreneur Programme (SEP), launched by Spirit of Enterprise (SOE), is a recognized program providing foundational entrepreneurship knowledge, practical business management skills, hands-on experience, and networking for secondary students. It is regarded as a strong example of best practice, especially for its experiential learning and mentorship components.</p>
<p>Mifras</p>		<p>Mifras aligns with EE best practices by training educators to deliver foundational knowledge, practical skills, and hands-on experiences to secondary students, supported by networking and mentorship. Its focus on teacher preparation ensures sustainable, scalable impact, making it a model for educational entrepreneurship. Its “3D Entrepreneurship” model fosters hands-on experience through action-oriented projects, such as mock enterprises addressing community issues, while connecting educators across 200+ schools impacting over 10,000 teachers and 120,000 students to facilitate networking with community stakeholders. Mifras further supports mentorship by guiding educators who, in turn, mentor students, enhancing self-efficacy through role modeling.</p>
<p>Unistream</p>		<p>Unistream is an Israeli non-profit that empowers underserved youth through hands-on entrepreneurship education. Its best practices include multi-year, team-based startup projects, strong industry mentorship, integration of STEM and business skills, real-world competitions, and inclusive outreach to diverse communities. Unistream’s model emphasizes experiential learning, professional networking, and practical business creation preparing youth for economic success and social impact.</p>

Tech-Driven Platforms in Entrepreneurship Education

These platforms were selected for their diverse and innovative use of technology in delivering entrepreneurship education. They represent a mix of AI-driven personalization, gamified and interactive learning experiences, immersive simulations, and mobile/SMS-based accessibility tools. Their inclusion showcases a broad spectrum of digital delivery models from high-tech adaptive systems to accessible low-tech solutions highlighting the range of technological approaches currently shaping entrepreneurship education globally.

Table 6: Tech-Driven Platforms in Entrepreneurship Education

Organization name	Logo	Description
GameYES		(Europe, Multilingual): A gamified entrepreneurship education platform that uses interactive simulations and AI-driven feedback to teach business concepts in multiple languages, enhancing engagement and learning outcomes across diverse European audiences.
GoVenture (Global)		EYE demonstrates the value of a longitudinal entrepreneurship education pipeline—spanning from primary to tertiary education. It An award-winning business simulation software that employs AI to create realistic virtual business environments, allowing learners worldwide to practice decision-making and entrepreneurship skills. underscores the impact of early and sustained exposure to entrepreneurial skills and values, which is essential in shaping future-ready learners.
Sandpit (UK/Global)		A global innovation platform combining AI and collaborative problem-solving to foster entrepreneurial thinking and creativity among students and early-stage entrepreneurs.
SimVenture (UK/Global)		A simulation-based learning platform that uses AI to model business scenarios, enabling users to experiment with startup strategies and understand market dynamics in a risk-free setting.
Hubro (Norway/Global)		A digital entrepreneurship education tool that uses AI to personalize learning experiences, helping users develop business skills through simulations and adaptive content.
FamBiz (BUILD) (USA)		A family business-focused entrepreneurship program that incorporates digital tools and AI analytics to help participants understand business management and succession planning.

Virtonomics (Global)		An online business strategy game powered by AI algorithms, where players manage virtual companies and compete in a dynamic marketplace, developing entrepreneurial skills through experiential learning.
YEP Africa (Africa)		Community-focused EE using team-based activities. Technological and pedagogical gaps limit impact. Wavumbuzi can learn from its SEL emphasis and peer collaboration.
Future Founders		Entrepreneurship Program at the International Incubation Center, which offers a 5-week intensive for university students to build MVP-level startups through structured modules covering startup basics, team building, ideation, and product testing
Solve Education		A gamified learning platform that uses AI-powered tools like Edbot.ai to deliver personalized learning experiences. It includes entrepreneurship modules and community features to enhance engagement and retention
Eneza		A mobile-first edtech platform delivering curriculum-aligned content via SMS, web, and Android. It uses AI to personalize learning and has recently merged with Knowledge Platform to expand its reach across Africa and Asia
Startup Wars		Offers realistic entrepreneurship simulations for students to practice business decision-making.. SAP ERPsim is a business simulation using real SAP systems, widely used in universities to teach enterprise operations and strategy. Both platforms are AI-enhanced and experiential, offering safe environments for learning through failure and iteration.
M-Shule (Kenya)		Africa's first AI-powered adaptive learning platform delivered via SMS and WhatsApp. It provides personalized micro-lessons in literacy, numeracy, and entrepreneurship, especially for learners without internet access.

LEO Startup School (Global)		A digital incubator platform using AI-driven mentorship and personalized learning paths to accelerate early-stage startups globally.
Kytabu		A digital textbook subscription service that uses AI to personalize content for students. It supports entrepreneurship education through interactive, gamified, and curriculum-aligned learning tools tailored to individual needs.
TrepCamp		An international entrepreneurship training academy designed to prepare aspiring entrepreneurs for high-impact ventures through immersive, hands-on programs in leading global business ecosystems.

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